

MOTIVATION AND PARTICIPATION OF FARMERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOY PLANT-BASED EXPANSION PROGRAM

(Case Study in Pakijangan Village, Wonorejo District, Pasuruan Regency)

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ABSTRACT

Along with the increasing need for agricultural products in the country and the limitations of domestic production due to land transfer, the Indonesian government designed a soy plant-based expansion program. It aims to meet food needs and increase farmers' income by expanding rice fields, optimizing land through raising the land index (LI), and optimizing other agricultural land and soybean farming activities. The expansion of soybean planting area is done by utilizing abandoned land or called *berah*, increasing the land index, new land clearing, cooperation on agricultural land use, forest people program, plantations, transmigration land, and other land potentials. The present study used purposive sampling in Pakijangan Village, Wonorejo District, Pasuruan Regency. The result revealed that some stakeholders actively involved in the plant expansion program were SHS. Inc., *Maju Bersama* agricultural kiosks, NGOs, Department of Agriculture, village government, and Development Planning Agency at Sub-National Level that contributes 65% or in the high category. The highest contribution of program implementation was served by the Department of Agriculture estimated by 61.14% or in the high category, and 63.87% or in the high category in the monitoring and evaluation stage. The farmer's motivation was mainly driven by an intrinsic factor namely, the age factor reached 66.67%. Last, the motivation level at the socialization stage reached 17.55%, the implementation stage served 35.55% or in the high category, and the monitoring and evaluation stage marked up 34.45%.

INTRODUCTION

Food needs are mandatorily fulfilled by every country, including Indonesia as it is the daily basic needs consumed by all people (Andri, 2012). Food is not only a basic need but it is also considered a human effort to maintain their survival and health as it provides the energy needed for people to work productively. One of the important food crop commodities for mass consumption and becoming a source of energy is soybeans (Sugiyanto & Pintakami, 2021).

Population growth is being accompanied by an increase in food demand. With the country's growing need for agricultural products and limited local output due to land transfer, the government meets the demand by importing agricultural commodities, notably soybean commodities. In 2015, Indonesia's national soybean needs were expected to reach 2.5 million-2.6 million tons. As a result, because the national soybean output supply was estimated to be only roughly 950,000 tons, the demand could be met by importing the commodities (Ministry of Industry and Trade, 2015). According to Central Statistics Agency data from 2016, the area of soybean harvest reached 220,815 hectares, a fall of 9,450 hectares from 2017 when it only reached 211,360 hectares (BPS, 2017).

Reflecting on the issues, the government devised a program to address food demands while also attempting to enhance farmer revenue, known as the soybean Planting Area Expansion (PAE) program. It focuses on extending rice fields, improving land by boosting the land index (LI), and improving other agricultural land and soybean farming activities. The Planting Area Expansion (PAE) program expands soybean planting areas by exploiting abandoned land, raising the land index, new land clearance, agricultural land use cooperation, forest people program, plantations, transmigration land, and other land potentials. The initiative is projected to be an alternative to boosting productivity by pursuing soybean farmer productivity levels (average 1.3 t/ha) with moderate-high genetic potential of soybean (genetic potential >2 t/ha) (Hamidah, 2016).

Pasuruan Regency is one of the places in the East Java Region that has adopted the Planting Area Expansion (PAE) program. Farmers in Pakijangan Village Wonorejo Subdistrict are the program's objective, and they are anticipated to be motivated and participate in the program's implementation. Farmers have received aid such as seeds and fertilizers, but participation in the program, which began in 2014, has been poor, and other issues have been discovered. Farmers' lack motivation contributes to their low engagement.

METHOD

The study site was specifically chosen in the Pakijangan Village Wonorejo Subdistrict Pasuruan Regency. In terms of the falling number of soybean farmers, the area is indicative. They prefer to cultivate corn after the rice growing season and because low soybean costs are less competitive with imported soybean prices. Furthermore, Pakijangan village is one among the areas in Pasuruan Regency that is implementing the Planting Area Expansion (PAE) program.

The research was carried out between March and May of 2021. This study collected data in two ways: primary data and secondary data. Primary data was gathered through field observations, interviews with respondents, and a questionnaire (Clark & Creswell, 2015), while secondary data was gathered from the Central Statistics Agency about soybean planting and production, books, the internet, and periodicals.

The census technique was used to determine the sample (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). It is appropriate with the research aim that was projected to the farmers who implement Planting Area Expansion (PAE) program. Using the sampling technique and the information from Wonorejo Subdistrict Office, the present study involved 30 farmers joining the program.

Two data analyses were employed in this study: descriptive analysis and Spearman Rank Correlation analysis (Yunus & Rezki, 2020). Descriptive analysis is used to answer research questions, such as describing parties involved in the soybean planting area expansion program, describing intrinsic and extrinsic factors that influence farmers' motivation to join the soybean planting area expansion program, analyzing the level of farmers' participation in the program beginning with the planning stage, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation, and describing the program itself (Sugiyono, 2017).

A scoring table was used to measure the parties involved in the program and their contributions and the significance of intrinsic and extrinsic factors toward farmers' motivation and participation, farmers' level of participation, and the program success analysis. The scoring table used the Likert scale (Brilliant et al., 2013).

The study used Spearman Rank Correlation to measure the correlation between intrinsic and extrinsic factors and farmers' motivation and participation and also program success. Further, the computation results were ranked from variable x and y, and then square and sum di^2 . Later, it was calculated using the following formula:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^n di^2}{n^3 - n}$$

r_s = Spearman's rank correlation coefficient

di = different between X and Y

n = number of observations

When the proportion of the same number is large, then a convection factor was used:

$$T = \frac{t^3 - t}{12}$$

t = the same number of observations in a rank

The following formula was used when the same number of observations was significant:

$$r_s = \frac{\sum X^2 + \sum Y^2 - \sum d^2}{\sqrt{(\sum X^2)(\sum Y^2)}}$$

$$\sum X^2 = \frac{n^3 - n}{12} - \sum T_x$$

$$\sum Y^2 = \frac{n^3 - n}{12} - \sum T_y$$

The significant r_s was computed using t-test:

$$T = r_s \sqrt{\frac{n - 2}{1 - r_s^2}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Parties Involved in the Soybean Planting Area Expansion Program

Based on field observation, parties involved in the program consisted of government and non-governmental parties. The governmental organizations were the Department of Agriculture, village government, and subnational government, while the non-governmental parties were Sang Hyang Seri. Inc., *Maju Bersama* agricultural kiosks, and NGOs. All parties were involving the dissemination stage, implementation, and monitoring, and evaluation. The non-governmental parties, especially *Maju Bersama* agricultural kiosks had a medium contribution of 56.1% in the program. The following is the recap of the non-governmental parties' involvement:

Table 1. The Non-Governmental Parties in the Soybean Planting Area Expansion Program

No.	Non Governmental Parties' Involvement	Number of Respondents	Level of Involvement %								
			SHS. Inc.			<i>Maju Bersama</i> agricultural kiosks			NGOs		
			Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
1.	Dissemination	30									
	a. Dissemination of planting area expansion program		-	23.3	76.7	-	26.7	73.3	-	66.7	3.3
	b. Dissemination of social assistance		3.3	66.7	30	36.7	63.3	-	-	36.7	63.3
2.	Implementation										
	a. Means of production usage		20	80	-	-	46.7	53.3	-	70	30
	b. Means of production		40	60	-	36.7	60	3.3	-	76.7	23.3
	c. Post-harvest	63.3	36.7	-	40	60	-	-	66.7	33.3	
3.	Monitoring & Evaluation										

	a. Monitoring		53.3	46.7	-	26.7	73.3	-	66.7	33.3	-
	b. Reporting		46.7	53.3	-	36.7	63.3	-	53.3	46.7	-
Average			75.3	19	7.5	35.3	56.1	18.5	17.1	56.5	36.6
Ranking			III			II			I		

Source: Primary data processed, 2021

Based on the table, SHS. Inc. marked 75.3% in the low category, *Maju Bersama* agricultural kiosks reached 56.5% in the medium category, and NGOs marked 56.5% in the medium category. The involvement of SHS. Inc. was low than *Maju Bersama* agricultural kiosks because it has less involvement in the activity. NGOs contributed to providing soybean seeds to farmers, even though the seeds were of poor quality. Some of the farmers used the seeds and the rest sold them and buy better seeds quality.

Maju Bersama agricultural kiosks reached 56.5% in the medium category which means the kiosks were involved only once in the planting area expansion program. The kiosk provided means of production for farmers. The kiosks also facilitate the farmers to exchange their soybean seeds for better quality. The level of involvement of the kiosks was medium because it contributes to the beginning stage of farming activities. Moreover, NGOs provided various assistance for farmers. The following table describes the government's involvement in the soybean planting area expansion program.

Table 2. Governmental Organizations Involved in the Soybean Planting Area Expansion Program

No.	Governmental Parties' Involvement	Number of Respondents	Level of Involvement %								
			Department of Agriculture			Village government			Subnational Government		
			Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
1.	Dissemination	30									
	a. Dissemination of planting area expansion program		-	30	70	-	30	70	-	30	70
	b. Dissemination of social assistance		3.3	43.3	53.3	3.3	36.7	60	-	40	60

2.	Implementation									
	a. Means of production usage	3.3	36.7	60	63.3	36.7	-	26.7	73.3	-
	b. Means of production	3.3	26.7	70	66.7	33.3	-	33.3	66.7	-
	c. Post-harvest	6.7	40	53.3	-	30	70	46.7	53.3	-
3.	Monitoring & Evaluation									
	a. Monitoring	10	26.7	63.3	46.7	50	3.3	56.7	43.3	-
	b. Reporting	6.7	30	63.3	53.3	43.3	3.3	60	40	-
Average		5.5	33.3	61.8	33.3	37.1	35.4	33.9	49.5	18.5
Ranking		I			II			III		

Source: Primary data processed, 2021

From the table, it is understood that the Agriculture Department reached an average score of 61.8% in the high category, its involvement is included in the high category. It is higher than village government with an average score of 37.1% in the medium category and subnational government with an average score of 49.7% in the medium category. The results implied that the parties were influential in the implementation of the program; however, more participation is needed.

The Agricultural Department has a high contribution in disseminating stage until the reporting stage. It also assisted such as providing means of production usage, doing field surveys, providing problem-solving, and assisting reports. The assistance from the department was well received by the farmers (Tania et al., 2013).

The second aim of the present study was focused on describing factors influencing farmers' motivation in the soybean planting area expansion program.

Table 3. Factors Influencing Farmers' Motivation

Factors Influencing Farmers' Motivation		Number of Respondents	Level of Influence (%)			Ranking
			Low	Medium	High	
Intrinsic	1. Age	30				
	a. < 40		-	16.7	-	II
	b. 40-60		-	-	66.6	I
	c. > 60		16.6	-	-	III
	2. Education					
	a. Elementary School		-	-	66.6	I
	b. Junior High School		-	16.7	-	II
	c. ≥ Senior High School		16.6	-	-	III
	3. Experience					
	a. <10 years		3.3	-	-	III
	b. 10-20 years		-	43.4	-	II
	c. >20 years		-	-	53.3	I
	4. Capital					
	a. <Rp.3,700,000		10	-	-	III
	b. Rp. 3,700,000		-	-	46.7	I
	c. >Rp. 3,700,000		-	43.3	-	II
	5. Income					
	a. <Rp.1,000,000		13.3	-	-	III
b. Rp. 1,000,000	-	-	46.7	I		
c. >Rp.1,000,000	-	40	-	II		
Average	3.9	10.6	17.9			
Extrinsic	1. Agricultural Extension	30				
	a. Passif		10	-	-	II
	b. Active		-	10	-	II
	c. Very Active		-	-	80	I
	2. Organization					
	a. Absent		10	-	-	III
	b. Registered in 1 organization		-	20	-	II
	c. Registered in more than 2 organizations		-	-	70	I
	3. Social assistance					
	a. Not helpful		-	-	-	III
	b. Helpful for farming		-	26.6	-	II
	c. Very helpful for farming		-	-	73.4	I
	Average		10	18.87	74.47	

Source: Primary data processed, 2021

From the table above, it can be concluded that the most influential factor both in intrinsic or extrinsic was agricultural by 80% in the high category, followed by social assistance by 73%, and the least factors, income, and capital by 46.7% in the high category. In short, all the factors were influential but different in the degree of influence.

Farmers' Participation in the Soybean Planting Area Expansion Program

The following is a recap of farmers' participation in the soybean planting area expansion program.

Table 4. Farmers' Participation in the Soybean Planting Area Expansion Program

No.	Farmers' Participation		Number of Respondents	Level of participation (%)			Ranking
				Low	Medium	High	
1.	Dissemination Stage	Attendance in the event	30	3.3	30	66.6	I
		Farmers' voice		60	23.3	16.7	II
		Average		31.6	26.6	46.3	
2.	Implementation Stage	Means of production usage	30	33.3	40	26.7	II
		Farming		16.7	43.3	40	I
		Post-harvest		63.3	23.3	13.3	III
		Average		37.8	35.5	26.7	
3.	Monitoring and Evaluation Stage	Controlling	30	-	60	40	I
		Reporting		13.3	50	36.7	II
		Average	30	6.65	55	38.35	

Source: Primary data processed, 2021

The table presents that farmers had high participation in the dissemination stage with a score of 46.3%. It happened because the meeting is important to attend as it conveyed information from the Department of Agriculture Pasuruan. Otherwise, the farmers' participation in the socialization of the social assistance was low supported by the data marked by 60% that illustrated some of the farmers were passive to give input and feedback. In the implementation stage, farmers' participation was low marked by 37.8% due to the low quality of the seeds distributed by the Department of Agriculture. The farmers need to exchange the seeds with better-quality seeds (Yusra et al., 2020).

In the farming categories, some farmers followed the instruction from the Department of Agriculture and the rest did farming activities like the usual technique. Moreover, in the monitoring and evaluation stage, the farmers' participation was moderate marked 53.3% because they were less active in the monitoring activities. Besides, the problem solving and report were made by group administration. Based on the above data, it can be concluded that farmers were actively involved in the disseminating or planning stage and had the least participation in the implementation stage.

The Relationship between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Factors towards Farmers' Motivation in the Soybean Planting Area Expansion Program

Analysis of the relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic factors with participation explains the significant relation or closeness of two variables. The analysis was to answer the contribution of intrinsic and extrinsic factors to farmers' motivation in the soybean planting area expansion program, including the dissemination, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation stage. The Spearman Rank Correlation was used to calculate the relationship with the symbol r_s count. If the r_s was larger than the r_s table, it meant that the implementation had a relationship with the management of the soy planting area expansion program.

Table 5. The Correlation between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Factors and Dissemination Stage

No	Variable X Motivation Factors	Number of Respondent s	Variabel Y (Dissemination)			
			Low	Mediu m	High	Rs count
1.	Intrinsic Factors	30				0.743
	a. Age		16.6	16.7	66.6	0.383*
	b. Education		16.6	16.7	66.6	0.548*
	c. Farming Experience		3.3	43.4	53.3	0.156
	d. Capital		10	43.3	46.7	0.710*
	e. Income		13.3	40	46.7	0.653*
2.	Extrinsic Factors					0.591
	a. Agricultural Extension		10	10	80	0.546*
	b. Organization		10	20	70	0.547*
	c. Social Assistance		-	26.6	73.4	0.271

Source: Primary data processed, 2021

Based on table 5, intrinsic factors such as farming experience had no relation with the farmers' motivation and participation in joining the soybean planting area expansion program. The computation showed $R_s 0.05 = 0.364$ where the calculation $r_s = 0.156 < r_s \text{ table} = 0.836$.

On the other hand, capital had a high correlation with the farmers' motivation and participation with a value of $t_{\text{calculate}} = 5,339$ and $r_s \text{ calculated} = 0,710 > r_s \text{ table} = 0,364$. The age factor has a value $t_{\text{calculate}} = 2,192$ and $r_s \text{ calculate} = 0,383 > r_s \text{ table} = 0,364$. Thus, it can be explained that the intrinsic factor was related in the planning stage with the hypothesis, the higher the economic benefits gather, the higher the participation. Likewise with age, the nearer farmer to the productive period of 40-60 years, the more motivated to follow the program. The relationship of intrinsic factors to the implementation of the program is presented in the following table:

Table 6. The Correlation between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Factors and Implementation Stage

No	Variable X Motivation Factors	Number of Respondent s	Variable Y (Implementation)				
			Low	Mediu m	High	Rs count	
1.	Intrinsic Factors	30				0,743	
	a. Age		16,6	16,7	66,6	0,470*	
	b. Education		16,6	16,7	66,6	0,580*	
	c. Farming Experience		3,3	43,4	53,3	0,192	
	d. Capital		10	43,3	46,7	0,446*	
	e. Income		13,3	40	46,7	0,614*	
2.	Extrinsic Factors						0,591
	a. Agricultural Extension		10	10	80	0,495*	
	b. Organization		10	20	70	0,708*	
	c. Social Assistance		-	26,6	73,4	0,221	

Source: Primary data processed, 2021

The table above depicted the relationship between intrinsic factors and the farmers' motivation and participation in joining the program (Bruch et al., 1972). In intrinsic factor indicators, not all indicators had a relationship with the implementation stage. The intrinsic factors that had significant relation, significance level of $R_s 0,05 = 0,364$, with the farmers' motivation and participation were education with a value of $t_{\text{calculate}} = 3,772$ and $r_s \text{ calculated} = 0,580 > r_s \text{ table} = 0,364$ and income with a value of $t_{\text{count}} = 4,112$ and $r_s \text{ calculated} = 0,614 > r_s \text{ table} = 0,364$. Thus, it could be explained that the higher the level of education or the more knowledge the farmers have, the higher their motivation and participation. The second is income, the higher the capital they had, the more motivated and participated would be because they did not hesitate to take the risk. Consequently, their motivation and participation were (Momeni, 2020).

In extrinsic factors, not all indicators have a relationship entirely with the participation in the implementation stage. But of the three indicators, two extrinsic indicators had a relationship with the participation in the planning of program activities with a significance level of $R_s 0.05 = 0.364$, namely organization with a value of $t\text{-calculate} = 5,308$ and $r_s \text{ calculated} = 0.708 > r_s \text{ table} = 0.364$. Thus, it could be explained that the more organization that the farmers join, the higher their participation in the program. The organization could be a farmers group, unit village cooperative, family welfare program. The higher motivation and participation was gathered due to the number of networks and groups that are followed increased new insights and information about the world of agriculture (Rahmawati & Abdulkadir-Sunito, 2015). Furthermore, concerning the monitoring and evaluation stage can be seen as follows:

Tabel 7. The Correlation between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Factors and Monitoring and Evaluation Stage

No	Variable X Motivation Factors	Number of Respondent s	Variable Y (Monitoring and Evaluation)			
			Low	Medium	High	R_s
1.	Intrinsic Factors	30				0.743
	a. Age		16.6	16.7	66.6	0.395*
	b. Education		16.6	16.7	66.6	0.568*
	c. Farming Experience		3.3	43.4	53.3	0.072
	d. Capital		10	43.3	46.7	0.623*
	e. Income		13.3	40	46.7	0.712*
2.	Extrinsic Factors					0.591
	a. Agricultural Extension		10	10	80	0.402*
	b. Organization		10	20	70	0.685*
	c. Social Assistance		-	26.6	73.4	0.306

Source: Primary data processed, 2021

The table above illustrated the correlation between intrinsic factors and participation in the monitoring and evaluation stage (Hestiana & Edy, 2015). Not all indicators in the intrinsic category correlated with participation in the monitoring and evaluation stage. The related indicator with a significance level of $R_s 0.05 = 0.364$ was age with the value of calculation = 2,273 and $r_s \text{ calculated} = 0.395 > r_s \text{ table} = 0.364$. Thus, it can be understood that the older the farmers, the higher their motivation and participation since they have more knowledge and experience. They are more knowledgeable on the agricultural field since they were involved in agriculture from the new order era to the reformation period (Awaluddin et al., 2014).

In the extrinsic category, not all indicators had a relationship with participation in the monitoring and evaluation stage (Fakhruroji et al., 2020). The correlated indicator with a significance level of $R_s 0.05 = 0.364$ was organization with a value of $t\text{-calculate} = 4,981$ and $r_s \text{ calculated} = 0.685 > r_s \text{ table} = 0.364$. It happened due to broader social networks influencing the way how people perceive something. Consequently, it influences motivation and participation as the number of networks and groups increases information about agriculture (Hamidah, 2016).

Program Success Analysis

The success of a program can be measured from several aspects, one of which is the economic aspect as it is an essential aspect (Sugino, 2021). Economic aspects are the goal in the existence of this program because the existence of a program can later make farmers better. One aspect of the economy that is always considered is income (Waluyati, 2019). In this program, the success rate also looks in terms of farmers' income whether it has increased or even decreased after participating in the soy planting area expansion program (Yuniriyanti et al., 2019). The indicator of increasing income is measured from the increasing planting area.

Table 8. Program Success of Soybean Planting Area Expansion Program

No.	Indicator	Total Farmers	Before Program Implementation (%)			After Program Implementation (%)			Percentage of Change %	Ranking
			Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High		
1.	Planting area	30	66.67	26.67	6.67	0	40	60	53.3	I
2.	Production		6.67	73.33	20.00	0	60	30	10	III
3.	Income		26.67	53.33	20.00	0	65	35	15	II

Source: Primary data processed, 2021

Table 8 presented that the planting area in Pakijangan village experienced an increase of 50% from each farmer's score reached by 60%, followed by medium category 40%, and the low category 0%. The production indicator illustrated that the percentage of the low category was 0%, the medium 60%, and the high category 40%. In terms of income, after the farmers joined the program, the low category showed 0%, the medium category 65%, and the high category 35%. Last, after the implementation of the soybean planting area program, the planting area increased by 53.33%, while production and revenue did not experience a significant increase of only 10% and 15%. It happened due to less participation of farmers in each stage of the soybean planting area expansion program (Iskandar, 2017).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results conducted in Pakijangan Village Wonorejo Subdistrict Pasuruan Regency, it can be concluded that the parties involved in the activities of the soy planting area expansion program are SHS. Inc., *Maju Bersama* agricultural kiosks, NGOs, Department of Agriculture, village government, and Development Planning Agency at Sub-National Level. In the intrinsic category, age becomes the influential indicator of the level of farmers' motivation and participation. On the other hand, in the external factor, extension posits in the potential position to determine farmers' motivation and participation. The level of participation in the dissemination stage, implementation, and monitoring, and evaluation stages are moderate. Last, the success rate of implementing after implementing the soy planting area expansion program is significant, but it is not followed by production and income.

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